

Age-Specific Fecundity Table of the Cotton Mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) at Different Temperatures

Khalid Mohammed ✉
University of Mosul, Iraq

Abstract

Phenacoccus solenopsis Tinsley, a cotton mealybug, has emerged as a new pest of many trees and ornamental plants in Iraq. In the current study, the life table parameters of *Ph. solenopsis* were necessitating basic studies on its development and survival on potato sprouts at different temperatures (22, 26 and 28 °C). Data were analyzed based on the age-stage, two-sex life table analysis. Results showed differences in the duration of egg, larvae, pupae, and adults. Meanwhile, the life table parameters including intrinsic rate of increase (m_r), mean generation time (T) and net reproductive rate (R_0) were categorized increasingly based on the feeding on potato sprouts. Longevity was highest at 22°C, but decreased at 26°C and then increased at 28°C. *Ph. solenopsis* could develop and reproduce under all three temperatures, but the survival rate, development, and fecundity of were affected by temperature. The intrinsic rate of increase was lowest at 22 °C (0.02563) and it was significantly less than at 21 °C (0.04689) and then increased at 28 °C (0.03988). Furthermore, *Ph. solenopsis* had the largest mean generation time (50.56) at 22 °C. These results mean that *Ph. solenopsis* is less adapted to the lower temperatures (22 °C) among these three set temperatures. The values of net reproductive rate (R_0) were higher at 26°C than at 22 and 28°C.

Keywords: *Phenacoccus solenopsis*, biological cycle, fertility life table.

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Introduction

The cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), is a severe polyphagous invasive species that significantly damages plants of at least 200 host plants from 63 families, including cotton, food crops, fruits, ornamental plants, tobacco, and vegetables, with a preference for the families Asteraceae, Solanaceae, Malvaceae and Fabaceae (Wang et al., 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2015; Ben-Dov et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2010) and is widely distributed in 46 countries in various biogeographical zones, causing substantial crop losses (Wang et al., 2010; García et al., 2017). It is native to the Neartic region, originally described from USA by Tinsley (1898) (Ben-Dov et al., 2015; Tinsley, 1898) and has expanded its range to areas outside the North American continent such as India, Pakistan and China in Asia (Abbas et al., 2005; Wu & Zhang, 2009; Gullan & Martin, 2005), Brazil and Argentina in South American (Granara de Willink, 2003; Charleston et al., 2010), Australia (Abdul-Rassoul et al., 2015), and Iraq (Muhammad, 2007) and it is expected to invade other cotton productive countries of the world (Nagrare et al., 2011; Hodgson et al., 2008). *P. solenopsis* recorded as a new insect pest on ornamental plant *Lantana camara* (Verbenaceae) as well as other host plants for the first time in Iraq. Those insects observed initially

during August 2014 up to July 2015 in residential gardens on the outskirts of Baghdad city (Muhammad, 2007; Abdul-Rassoul et al., 2015).

Plants infested by mealybugs during vegetative phase exhibit symptoms of distorted, bushy shoots, crinkled and/or twisted bunchy leaves and stunted plants that dry completely in severe cases. Late season infestations during reproductive crop stage result in reduced plant vigor and early crop senescence. While feeding mealybugs injects a toxic substance into the plant parts resulting in chlorosis, stunting, deformation and death of plants (Haddad & Parra, 1984). Mealybugs attack all parts of the plant, particularly growing tips or leaves that join stems or along leaf veins causing both direct and indirect damage to the plant, direct damage is caused by sucking sap from leaves, twig, stem, roots and fruiting bodies, and indirectly by deposition of honeydew that gives rise to sooty mold growth blocking light and air from the leaves and reducing photosynthesis productivity (Wagner et al., 1984; Abdul-Rassoul et al., 2015).

Understanding the changes in species' niches is not only a central topic in ecology and evolution but also is especially important in the study of biological invasions (Sharpe & DeMichele, 1977). Alien species survive under new climate conditions that are different from those in their native range owing to a lack of natural enemies or local adaptation when introduced into new geographic areas. Hence, testing niche changes between native and non-native ranges is crucial for understanding range expansion and the potential invasive range (Wei et al., 2017). The development of an adequate control strategy, with minimal pesticide use, requires basic knowledge on the pest's population dynamics (Sandhu et al., 2013). Mathematical models are commonly used to predict the occurrence of agricultural pests (Martins et al., 2016; Fonseca Lacerda et al., 2019; Parra et al., 2022). Among the components of a model, temperature is one of the most important climatic elements for the development and survival of many insect species (Kakde et al., 2014; Pereira et al., 2023). Since insects are poikilothermic, i.e., adapt to the ambient temperature, this thermal constant also applies to their development (Sirisena et al., 2013; Pereira et al., 2023). Combining life table data with the study of thermal requirements makes it possible to show the patterns of survival and reproduction of a given population at different temperatures (Al-Omairy, 2009; Singh, 1978; IBM Corp., 2013; Elliott et al., 1988; Pereira et al., 2023). Life tables are an important tool for understanding insect population dynamics and to produce basic knowledge for additional studies, such as behavioral analysis, mass rearing, response to control agents, among others. It provides a summary description of age specific mortality rate, survivorship for each developmental stage and reproduction and it is useful in revealing the maximal growth potential of a population. From a pest management standpoint, it is very important to know the most susceptible stage of the pest and therefore the most opportune periods for its control (Pielou, 1977; Herrero et al., 2018).

Therefore, in order to contribute with helpful information for the management of this pest species (Herrero et al., 2018), the aim of this study was the development of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* reared on potato spots and pumpkin at four different temperatures, determined its thermal development limits, and generated a fertility life table.

Materials and Methods

Insect Collection and Identification

A mass of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* were collected with infested plant parts in May 2023 manually from many ornamental plants in Mosul (36° 20' 24.0000" N and 43° 7' 48.0036" E), Ninawah, Iraq. The samples then placed in plastic cages (20 cm high and 10 cm diameter) and transported to the laboratory. The adults were identified using a compound microscope (10x40) at the college of Agriculture and forestry, University of Mosul.

Potato Sprouts as Host for Mealybug Cultures

The mealybugs were reared in the laboratory using potatoes following the modified method recommended by (Al-Omairy, 2009; Singh, 1978). Potato sprouts (*Solanum tuberosum*) were used to rear *Phenacoccus solenopsis*. Potatoes were washed with tap water to remove soil and dust particles attached to the surface and pat dry using tissue papers. Surface sterilization of potato was done by using 4% Sodium hypochlorite to remove possible pathogens. Minor damaged and open spots on the potato surface were covered by hot paraffin wax coating to prevent secondary infections and allowed to dry (Gunawardana & Hemachandra, 2020). Cleaned potatoes were kept for 48 hours to remove the adverse effect of Sodium hypochlorite on mealybugs. Potatoes were air dried in good ventilated laboratory conditions (26–30 °C, R.H- 70- 80%) (Gunawardana & Hemachandra, 2020). Potato put on dark moistened plastic boxes 50x30x20 cm. Water was sprinkled daily to keep the plastic boxes moistened to encourage sprouting. After 4 weeks, potatoes produced sprouts of 4-6 cm. Then the insects were transferred with a camel hair brush to the potato sprouts and reared under laboratory conditions of 25°C, 65 ± 5% RH and a photoperiod of 12 hrs.

Age-Specific Fecundity Tables Parameters

A certain number of eggs were taken from the isolated adult female's immediately after deposition and placed on potato sprouts until hatching (El-Aw et al., 2016). 20 virgin females were isolated soon after the third moult and observed daily to record the daily survival rate (l_x). The laid eggs were calculated daily and removed from beneath adult females. The duration periods of immature stages of 1st, 2nd and 3rd instar were calculated (El-Aw et al., 2016). Daily adult numbers observation from the first day of female eclosion until complete females death, daily survival rate (l_x) and female fecundity (m_x) were calculated according to equation of life tables to predict the growth rate of the population under laboratory conditions of temperatures under 22±1°C, 26±1°C and 28±1°C (El-Aw et al., 2016). From the fertility and survival schedules, several population growth parameters including the net reproductive rate (R_0), mean generation time (T) and intrinsic rate of natural increase (rm) were calculated according to (30):

$$I_x = n_x \setminus n_0$$

That which is:

I_x : Survival rate during the age stage x .

n_x : Number of individuals at the end of age stage x .

n_0 : Number of individuals at the beginning of age stage x .

The m_x values for all age stages of *S. cretica* were divided by 2 to extract the average number of females produced at each age stage. By knowing the lifetime survival rates and lifetime productivity rates, the net reproductive rate (R_0), mean generation time (T), and the intrinsic rate of increase were extracted as follows (Najem & Mohammed, 2025):

$$R_0 = \sum I_x m_x \quad (1)$$

That which is:

R_0 : Net reproductive rate which refer to average number of offspring produced by an individual in its lifetime (The number of females produced \ female \ generation).

$\sum I_x m_x$: The sum of multiplying the lifetime survival rates of females by the lifetime productivity rates.

$$T = \sum_x (I_x m_x) \backslash \sum I_x m_x \quad (2)$$

That which is:

T: Mean generation time

$\sum_x (I_x m_x)$: The sum of the multiplication of $I_x m_x$ in the age stage x

$\sum I_x m_x$: Net reproductive rate

r_m : $\text{Log } R_o \backslash T$

r_m : The intrinsic rate of increase in population

$\text{Log } R_o$: The inverse of the logarithm of the net reproductive rate

T: Mean generation time

Results and Discussion

The production and survival of the cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* in laboratory conditions at constant temperatures of (22, 26 and 28°C) are showed in Tables (1, 2, and 3). They demonstrate how temperatures affect the life span of the pest, the age rates of females at first reproduction, in addition to their effect on the females' egg production rates. The average life span of females reared on potato sprouts at the mentioned temperatures was 16, 22 and 22 days, respectively. The average preoviposition was 6, 4 and 2 days, respectively. The average number of eggs laid by females at the mentioned temperatures was 79.59, 268.61 and 184.46 eggs, respectively.

The nature of population fluctuations in insects is described by a measure of growth and reproduction rates derived from productivity and survival tables, which include the net reproductive rate (R_o) and the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) in the population. According to the results of the net reproductive rate (R_o) per female at the temperatures shown in Table 4, the *Ph. solenopsis* population is not thought to be a stable species. The values of R_o were 19.77, 81.32 and 54.42 female \ female \ generation at the temperatures of 22, 26 and 28°C, respectively. It is noted that the net reproductive rate value was 81.32 female \ female \ generation at a temperature of 26°C. This may be attributed to the high survival rates of *Ph. solenopsis* stages at this temperature, which reached 0.88, in addition to the high ability of females to lay eggs, as the egg production rate at this temperature reached 268.61 eggs, while the lowest value of the net reproductive rate was 19.77 female \ female \ generation at a temperature of 22°C, due to the approximately low survival rates at this temperature, which was 0.74, and the low productivity at a rate of 79.59 eggs.

It is clear from the above that the net reproductive rate increases with the increase in temperature to a certain extent, then it begins to decrease as the temperature exceeds the optimum rate for survival and reproduction. This is consistent with what (Engelmann, 2013) mentioned, which is that the effect of temperature on productivity is similar to its effect on growth rate. At the optimum temperature, productivity is at its maximum possible; then, it declines if the temperature decreases or increases above this limit.

Table 1. Age-Specific Fecundity Table of the Cotton Mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at 22°C

X	lx	Mx	mx	lxmx	Xlxmx
1-38	Immature stages				
39-44	Preoviposition				
45	0.74	1.82	0.73	0.54	24.31
46	0.74	3.80	1.52	1.12	51.74
47	0.74	4.40	1.76	1.30	61.21
48	0.66	5.78	2.31	1.52	73.18
49	0.66	10.90	4.36	2.88	141.00
50	0.66	8.20	3.28	2.16	108.24
51	0.66	10.77	4.31	2.84	145.07
52	0.63	11.18	4.47	2.81	146.44
53	0.61	7.10	2.84	1.73	91.82
54	0.61	4.66	1.86	1.13	61.27
55	0.44	5.83	2.33	1.02	56.39
56	0.38	2.16	0.86	0.33	18.30
57	0.38	1.71	0.68	0.26	14.73
58	0.20	1.28	0.51	0.10	5.92
59	0.14	0	0	0	0
60	0.10	0	0	0	0
61	0	0	0	0	0
Total	-	79.59	31.84	19.77	999.61

Table 2. Age-Specific Fecundity Table of the Cotton Mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at 26°C

X	lx	Mx	mx	lxmx	Xlxmx
1-29	Immature stages				
30-33	Preoviposition				
34	0.88	1.44	0.58	0.51	17.23
35	0.88	3.33	1.33	1.17	41.02
36	0.88	15.10	6.04	5.31	191.35
37	0.88	17.62	7.05	6.20	229.48
38	0.88	22.16	8.86	7.80	296.41
39	0.88	23.60	9.44	8.31	323.98
40	0.88	37.28	14.91	13.12	524.90
41	0.88	31.12	12.45	10.95	449.12
42	0.67	19.13	7.65	5.13	215.32
43	0.67	19.68	7.87	5.27	226.79
44	0.67	18.88	7.55	5.06	222.63
45	0.67	17.62	7.05	4.72	212.50
46	0.67	11.22	4.49	3.01	138.32
47	0.44	11.45	4.58	2.01	94.71
48	0.44	8.67	3.47	1.52	73.24
49	0.32	5.30	2.12	0.68	33.24
50	0.32	1.78	0.71	0.23	11.39
52	0.32	1.90	0.76	0.24	12.65
53	0.18	0.67	0.27	0.05	2.56
54	0.10	0.66	0.26	0.03	1.42
55	0.10	0	0	0	0
56	0	0	0	0	0
Total	-	268.61	107.44	81.32	3318.26

Table 3. Age-Specific Fecundity Table of the Cotton Mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at 28°C

X	lx	Mx	mx	lxmx	Xlxmx
1-34	Immature stages				
35-36	Preoviposition				
37	0.83	2.12	0.848	0.70384	26.04208
38	0.83	4.96	1.984	1.64672	62.57536
39	0.83	10.28	4.112	3.41296	133.1054
40	0.83	15.27	6.108	5.06964	202.7856
41	0.83	22.11	8.844	7.34052	300.9613
42	0.80	18.73	7.492	5.9936	251.7312
43	0.80	18.22	7.288	5.8304	250.7072
44	0.80	15.10	6.04	4.832	212.608
45	0.80	14.29	5.716	4.5728	205.776
46	0.80	12.13	4.852	3.8816	178.5536
47	0.80	12.18	4.872	3.8976	183.1872
48	0.58	11.18	4.472	2.59376	124.5005
49	0.44	7.77	3.108	1.36752	67.00848
50	0.44	5.18	2.072	0.91168	45.584
51	0.44	5.83	2.332	1.02608	52.33008
52	0.44	3.26	1.304	0.57376	29.83552
53	0.44	2.88	1.152	0.50688	26.86464
54	0.22	2.15	0.86	0.1892	10.2168
55	0.22	0.82	0.328	0.07216	3.9688
56	0.12	0	0	0	0
57	0.12	0	0	0	0
58	0.05	0	0	0	0
59	0	0	0	0	0
Total	-	184.46	73.78	54.42	2368.34

The results (Table 4) also showed that the average mean generation time (T) was 50.56, 40.80 and 43.52 days at temperatures of 22, 26 and 28°C, respectively. This means that, up to an optimum point, the rate of generation length reduces as temperature rises since, at that point, the influence of temperature turns inversely because insect growth rate increases with temperature. Additionally, (Elliott et al., 1988) mentioned that during the immature stages of an insect's life cycle, a slight decrease in growth rate is observed as a result of increasing temperature above the optimum limit. This decrease in growth rate results in an increase in the time required for development to be completed, extending the generation's duration.

Table 4. Net Reproductive Rate (Ro), Mean Generation Time (T), and Intrinsic Rate of Increase (rm) Derived from Age-Specific Fecundity Tables of Cotton Mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at Constant Temperatures

Temperature (°C)	Average lifespan of females (days)	Average of Preoviposition (days)	Average number of eggs/female (Mx)	Net reproductive rate (Ro)	Mean generation time (T)	Intrinsic rate of increase)rm(
22	16	6	79.59	19.77	50.56	0.02563
26	22	4	268.61	81.32	40.80	0.04689
28	22	2	184.46	54.42	43.52	0.03988

Conclusion

The results showed that the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) in *Ph. solenopsis* population was 0.02563, 0.04689 and 0.03988 female\ female\ day at temperatures of 22, 26 and 28°C, respectively; thus, this means the value of the intrinsic rate of increase in the population increases with the rise in temperature to reach its highest value at 26°C then it starts to gradually decrease as the temperature rises. (Pielou, 1977) mentioned that the value of the intrinsic rate of increase in the population increases when the rate of mean generation time decreases. (Amutha and Dharajothi, 2015) mentioned that the intrinsic capacity for increase (r_m) reached the maximum values at 30°C, which were 0.176. Intrinsic rate of increase was higher at 30°C followed by 25 and 20°C because the nymphs developed to adults faster at 30°C than at 20 and 25°C and produced more offspring sooner and that does not agree with what was reached in this paper.

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